

Kinetometrics. Part-I. KINTOB – A Tool Box for Kinetics

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Manuscript received 14 March 1997, accepted 18 August 1997

Kinetometrics, a subfield of chemometrics, is concerned with the application of statistical, mathematical and information methods to arrive at the best possible knowledge of rates of chemical reactions and mechanistic details. The errors in rate constants may be due to the random and systematic noise in response, transformation of equations to a linear form and inherent correlation between rate constants. A software package, KINTOB in the form of tool box is developed in MATLAB environment running on any microcomputer under DOS. KINTOB is modular and easily upgradable as the computations are implemented in matrix notation. Five major options are available in the package. In demonstration mode, typical literature data systems are available. In the calculation mode, the rate constant of any medium-slow kinetic reaction following zero, first, second or third order can be estimated by LLS, Kalman Filter (KF) and Gauss-Newton (GN) methods. In the third mode, simulation of kinetic systems can be performed which is also useful for model validation. Least median squares (LMS) method is used in the fourth option for linear variation of $\log k$ with ambient conditions (functions of ionic strength, temperature or dielectric constant). The fifth mode has a unique feature of investigating the error surfaces (3D and 2D contours) of rate constants or object function with errors in response and initial and final concentrations of the species.

The application of statistical and mathematical methods to different fields of study leads to the surge of new disciplines like econometrics, psychometrics, chemometrics and biometrics. Chemometrics¹ is the discipline concerned with the software implementation of statistical, mathematical and information algorithms to chemistry. In the recent past, subdisciplines like envirometrics, pharmacometrics, synthometrics, qualimetrics and speciometrics² have become popular. Now, another specialization 'Kinetometrics' dealing with the knowledge of rates of chemical reactions and mechanistic details is introduced.

Some of the objectives of kinetic study are given in Fig. 1. The information from product analysis, detection of intermediates and knowledge of reactive form of the reactants is utilized in supporting the mechanism. The variation of rate constant(s) as a function of substituent, concentration of hydrogen ion, ionic strength, temperature and solvent characteristics (one at a time) are ex-

plained by linear free energy relationships (LFER). Quantitative structure-activity relationships (QSAR) of which LFER is a subset and quantitative structure-property relationships (QSPR) are instrumental in developing heuristics regarding the activated complexes.

The application of kinetic investigations³ include estimation of nanogram quantities of compounds, synthesis of a desired substance with minimum side-reactions and speciation of metal-ligand interactions under equilibrium. Except a few discrete efforts, most of the data are acquired at the absorption maximum (single sensor) to estimate rate constants or to estimate concentrations by kinetic method of analysis. The hyphenation and the partial automation resulted in intelligent (virtual) instruments which increased precision. Yet most of the instruments are under-utilized. The rate constants or concentrations were estimated for most of the cases by the linear least squares (LLS)/graphical analysis and rarely by non-linear methods, like Marquardt, extended Kalman and Simplex. There are very few reports to arrive at optimum operating conditions in kinetic method of analysis by multiple linear regression using a full quadratic model.

During the last decade algorithmic⁵ and heuristic⁶⁻⁸ programs have been developed in this laboratory. In continuation of these efforts, a software package KINTOB (KINetic Tool Box) was developed in this study.

Formulation of the problem :

The sub-tasks involved in this project are (i) estimation of rate constant (k), (ii) variation of k with concentration or with ambient conditions, and (iii) simulation.

Estimation of rate constant : The differential and linear forms of $n^*R \rightarrow P$ type of reactions are given in Table 1.

Fig. 1. Some typical tasks of kinetics in solution phase.

TABLE 1—MATRIX REPRESENTATION OF LINEAR MODEL FOR INTEGRAL ORDER REACTIONS

Model : Resp = X*Par Data structure : [time Resp]

Resp = [resp₁ resp₂]^T, t = [t₁ t₂]^T, one = [1 1 1]^T

Type of reaction	Differential form of rate law	Linear form			Eqn.
		Response (Resp)	Measurement function (X)	Parameters (Par)	
0*R → P	$\frac{dP}{dt} = -\frac{dR}{dt} = k_0$	Resp	[one t]	$\begin{bmatrix} a_0 \\ k_0 \end{bmatrix}$	1
1*R → P	$\frac{dP}{dt} = k_1 * [\text{Resp}]_t$	log(a ₀ -x)	[one t]	[log a ₀ k ₁] ^T	2
2*R → P	$\frac{dP}{dt} = k_2 * [\text{Resp}]_t^2$	1/(a ₀ -x)	[one t]	[-1/a ₀ k ₂] ^T	3
n*R → P	$\frac{dP}{dt} = k_n * [\text{Resp}]_t^n$	1/(a ₀ -x) ⁿ⁻¹	[one t]	$\begin{bmatrix} -(n-1) \\ a_0^{n-1} (n-1)k_n \end{bmatrix}^T$	4
R ₁ + R ₂ + R ₃ → P	$\frac{dP}{dt} = k_3 * [a_0-x] * [b_0-x] * [c_0-x]$	5	[t]	[k]	6
	c ₀ = b ₀	7	[t]	[k]	
	$\ln \left[\left(\frac{a_0-x}{a_0} \right)^{b_0-c_0} * \left(\frac{b_0-x}{b_0} \right)^{c_0-a_0} * \left(\frac{c_0-x}{c_0} \right)^{a_0-b_0} \right]$	5		$(a_0-b_0) * (b_0-c_0) * (c_0-a_0)$	
	$7 \frac{1}{(a_0-b_0)^2} * \left[\frac{(a_0-b_0)*x}{b_0*(b_0-x)} + \ln \frac{a_0*(b_0-x)}{b_0*(a_0-x)} \right]$	7			

X = Concentration of product.

The transformed form of the response (Y) is a linear function (eqn. 1) of one variable (time, t) with two parameters, transformed form of initial concentration and rate constant (intercept and slope, respectively),

$$Y = f(t; k, a_0) = \text{Intercept} + \text{slope} * t \quad (1)$$

Since Y is a function of two parameters, at least two responses at different time intervals are needed to solve the two linear equations by elimination method. However, more experimental points (NP) are needed to estimate k over a range of time and concentration. One of the best methods for best linear unbiased estimator (BLUE) of a linear model is the least-squares method.

Estimation of rate constants of integral order reactions is a non-linear problem (NLP). The response which is proportional to the concentration at time t is represented as response (product or reactant) = F(k; a₀, t). The non-linear forms of equations and their first and second analytical derivatives with respect to k, initial and final concentrations are given in Table 2. A closed form of solution of a non-linear equation is not trivial. So, it is

TABLE 2—NON-LINEAR FUNCTIONAL FORM (x) OF INTEGRAL ORDER REACTIONS AND THEIR DERIVATIVES

Order of reaction	Non-linear equation	First derivative		Second derivative	
		$\frac{\partial x}{\partial k}$	$\frac{\partial x}{\partial a_0}$	$\frac{\partial^2 x}{\partial k^2}$	$\frac{\partial^2 x}{\partial a_0^2}$
	x = f(par)	$\frac{\partial x}{\partial k}$	$\frac{\partial x}{\partial a_0}$	$\frac{\partial^2 x}{\partial k^2}$	$\frac{\partial^2 x}{\partial a_0^2}$
I	$x = a_0 * [1 - \exp(-k_1 * t)]$	1	2		5
II	$x = \frac{a_0^2 * k_2 * t}{(1 + a_0^2 * k_2 * t)}$	3	4		
1	$\left[\frac{\partial x}{\partial k} = a_0 * x * \exp(-k_1 * x) \right]$			2	$\left[\frac{\partial x}{\partial a_0} = 1 - \exp(-k_1 * x) \right]$
3	$\frac{(1 + k_2 * a_0 * t) * a_0^2 * (t - a_0^2) * k_2 * t * (a_0 * t)}{(1 + a_0^2 * k_2 * t)^2}$				
4	$\frac{(1 + k_2 * a_0 * t) * (k_2 * t * 2 * a_0) - a_0^2 * (k_2 * t) * (k_2 * t)}{(1 + a_0^2 * k_2 * t)^2}$				
5	$[-a_0 * t * x * (\exp(-k_1 * t) * x * \exp(-k_1 * t))]$				

Transformation of a non-linear equation into a quadratic one in derivatives through Taylor's expansion :

Table-2 (contd.)

$$f(\text{par}) + g'^*s + s'^*H*s \cong 0 \dots\dots 6$$

where, $g = \left[\frac{\partial x}{\partial x} \frac{\partial x}{\partial a_0} \right]^T$, H = Hessian, $\text{par} = [k a_0]^T$

Refinement of parameters by iterative process

$$\text{Par}(i) = \text{Par}(i-1) + s \dots\dots\dots 7$$

expanded by Taylor series and truncated to first degree or second degree terms. Since the number of experimental points are greater than the number of parameters, a least-squares solution is sought. Since Taylor series is truncated, the process of iteration is needed to arrive at an acceptable solution based on the accuracy of the results needed.

In the case of second order reactions with different reactants, rate constants are estimated under pseudo-first

order and second order conditions keeping concentrations of reactants in a stoichiometric ratio. Here, generally, LLS is employed and the errors in the second order rate constant computed under first order conditions results in cumulative errors. The estimation of rate constants of the consecutive (A → B → C) and parallel (A → C; A → B) reactions pose problems depending upon the relative magnitudes of k_1 and k_2 and the species monitored. In chemical reactions occurring in the flame, atmosphere or those involving free radicals, the number of rate constants is very large and the simple integral or non-linear equations are impracticable. Hence, either numerical differentiation (Runga Kutta fourth or seventh order, Predictor-Corrector method) or integration (GEAR, Bulirsch-Stoer) procedures are used. But analytical differentiation,

TABLE 3—A HEURISTIC APPROACH FOR THE ESTIMATION OF RATE CONSTANT OF SECOND ORDER REACTION

Program : (kb_k2.m)
 $N1*A + N2*B \rightarrow N3*P$
 $N1 = N2 = 1$

Stoichiometric coefficients

Initial conc.

Monitoring species

	A	P	A	B	P	A	B	P	A	B	P	
Rule	1	1	3	4	2	6	7	5	9	10	8	
equation	3	3	11	12	11	13	13	13	14	14	14	
Information equation	a_0	Pinf	a_0	b_0	Pinf	X	b_0	a_0, b_0	a_0	X	Pinf	
Data structure	2	3	1	2	3	1		2	3	1	2	3

X = Not a good experimental design.

	$N1 \cdot A + N2 \cdot B \rightarrow N3 \cdot P$					
Stoichiometric coefficients	$N1 \neq N2$					
Initial conc.	$a_0 = b_0$			$a_0 \neq b_0$		
	$\frac{a_0}{b_0} = \frac{N1}{N2}$			$\frac{a_0}{b_0} \neq \frac{N1}{N2}$		
Monitoring species	Reactant		Product	Reactant		Product
	A	B	P	A	B	P
Rule	13	14	12	16	17	15
equation	11	12	11	11	12	11
Information	a_0	b_0	Pinf	a_0	b_0	Pinf
Intermediate calculation	101	102	99,100	101	102	99,100
Data	1	2	3	1	2	3
structure	$1 = [t \text{ amx}], \quad 2 = [t \text{ bmx}], \quad 3 = [t \text{ x}], \quad \text{amx} = [a_0 \cdot \text{one} - x]$					
Intermediate calculations :	101. $x = a_0 - \text{amx}; \text{bmx} = b_0 - x, 102. x = b_0 - \text{bmx}; \text{amx} = a_0 - x$ 100. $a_0 = \text{Pinf} \cdot N1; b_0 = \text{Pinf} \cdot N2, 99. \text{amx} = a_0 - x; \text{bmx} = b_0 - x;$					
	13. $Y = \ln(\text{bmx}); k_2 = \frac{k_1}{a_0}$ (program : eq- $a_0k_3.m$) 14. $Y = \ln(\text{amx}); k_2 = \frac{k_1}{b_0}$ (program : eq- $a_0k_3.m$)					

whenever possible, is preferred to integration or numerical methods.

Variation of k with concentration of ingredients: The change in the magnitude of k with the concentration of reactant(s) or hydrogen ion is used to determine the order of the reaction adopting one variable at a time (OVAT) method. The general practice is algebraic transformation of eqn. (1) to get a linear form under linear constraints (like $a_0 \gg b_0$ or $a_0 \ll b_0$). Some heuristics for the estimation of second order rate constant are given in Table 3. The integral orders for hydrogen ion are proposed in different regions rather than fitting it into a non-linear equation, $Y = f(\text{FH}, k; \text{par})$.

LLS yields unbiased estimators only when the errors in response are normal and there are no outliers. As the error distribution in $\log k$ with concentrations is unknown, Kalman filter is preferable. Least median squares

(LMS), a robust method to outliers, can be used to detect and filter the stray points.

Kinetic method of analysis : In kinetic method of analysis, the concentration(s) of an analyte (par) is estimated by monitoring the response (Resp) at a single sensor employing eqn. (2),

$$\text{Resp} = X \cdot \text{Par} \quad (2)$$

where X is the measurement function. The concentrations are estimated by the least-squares solution of eqn. (2). Table 4 incorporates the parameters and the corresponding measurement functions for a few popular types of kinetic models. LLS fails when k_1/k_2 is less than 5, where Kalman filter, Simplex and Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) result in reliable estimates.

Experimental design for optimum concentrations of reactants, catalyst, pH etc. resulted in higher sensitivity

TABLE 4—EQUATIONS USED IN KINETIC METHODS OF ANALYSIS

Reaction	Measurement function(x)	Parameters (par)
R → P	$[1 - \exp(-k_1 * t)]$	$[C_A C_{A_0}]^T$
2*R → P	$\left[\left(1 + \frac{1}{k_a * t} \right)^{-1} l \right]$	$[C_B C_{B_0}]^T$
R1 → P		
2*R2 → P	$\left[\{1 - \exp(-k_A * t)\} \left(1 + \frac{1}{k_b * t} \right)^{-1} l \right]$	$[C_A C_B C]^T$

$A \xrightarrow{k_A} B \xrightarrow{k_B} C$	
Par = (X*) * Resp	Resp : response
Res = Resp - X*Par	Res : residual

of the kinetic methods as compared to those performed by univariate optimization. Multiple linear regression (MLR) for full quadratic model of the variables (eqn. 3) and visual exploratory analysis by response surface methodology (RSM) gained popularity in the context,

$$Y = a_0 + a_1 * X_1 + a_2 * X_2 + a_3 * X_1 * X_2 + a_4 * X_1^2 + a_5 * X_2^2 \quad (3)$$

The variation of the response with one of the explanatory or influencing factor (X₁) at a constant value of the other can be represented by a line drawing in two-dimensional (2D) graph. The extremum in the plot is used to arrive at the optimum conditions. When the two influencing factors are interacting, a true optimum is obtained by simultaneous variation of the two variables. Now the variation of response is a surface in three-dimensional (3D) space. Generation of these plots is referred as response surface methodology. Interpolation techniques of increasing rigour are in use and the MATLAB's in-built facility is made use of in Canonical analysis, partial least-squares regression (PLSR) and ANN are proved to yield better results especially when the variables are highly correlated and several responses from different techniques or responses at several wavelengths (sensors) are measured. Central Composite and Box-Behnken Designs (CCD and BBD), experiments at random points and those to orthogonalize the available data are used to get maximum information regarding the optimum operating conditions.

Variation of k with ambient conditions: The rate constants are estimated at different temperatures, ionic strengths, solvent compositions of a water miscible solvent, micelle or cryptand. Each of these variations are performed with a specific purpose like computing activation energy, understanding the ionic character or solvent structure of the activated complex etc. Although

well-tested theoretical models exist, (Y_i = intercept + slope * X; X = 1/D, 1/T etc.) noticeable deviations have been observed when experiments are performed over a wide range of values for the ambient conditions. It led to propose empirical models mostly polynomial ones, Y = a₀ + a₁ * X₂ + a₂ * X₃ using regression methods. It appears that the residuals obtained after applying the well-established truncated models should be fitted into empirical models (need not be polynomial ones) as proposed by Kowalski in his concept of chemnets.

TABLE 5—EQUATIONS FOR SIMULATION OF CONCENTRATION OF SPECIES IN INTEGRAL ORDER REACTIONS

Type of reaction	Order	Conc. of product (X_SIM)	Equation
A → P	0	k*t	1
A → P	1	a ₀ * (1-exp(t))	2
2*A → P	2	$\frac{a_0^2 * k * t}{one + a_0 * k * t}$	3
A + B → P	2	$C = \frac{b_0}{a_0} * \exp[k * t * (b_0 - a_0)]$; if a ₀ ≠ b ₀ $\frac{a_0 * C - b_0 * one}{C - one}$	4
3*A → P	3	$a_0 * one - \sqrt{\frac{one * a_0^2}{2 * k * a_0^2 * t}}$	5
N1*A+N2*B → N3*P	2	$d = \frac{a_0}{b_0} * \exp \left[k_2 * t - n_2 * \left(a_0 - \frac{n_1}{n_2} * b_0 \right) \right]$ $X = \frac{b_0 * d - a_0}{\left(-\frac{n_1}{n_2} + d \right)}$	6 7
A → P and B → P (#)		$amx = a_0 - N1 * \frac{x}{N3}$ $amx = b_0 - N2 * \frac{x}{N3}$	8 9
		$X_1 = a_0 * [1 - \exp(-k_1 * t)]$ $X_2 = b_0 * [1 - \exp(-k_2 * t)]$ $X = X_1 + X_2$	10 11 12

Program : EQ_k_SIM1.m # : k_sim_11.m

Simulation : The equations for calculation of concentrations of the species with time for integral order and consecutive reactions are incorporated in Table 5. These equations have a closed form of solution and thus can be computed directly.

Computational methods in vogue :

A brief description of the present scenario of advanced statistical and mathematical procedures applied in chemical kinetics follows. Alcock *et al.*⁹ and Mullice and Cok¹⁰

published Fortran programs to estimate the rate constants of mono-, bi- and tri-phasic reactions adopting one of the best non-linear algorithms, namely, Marquardt. DeTar^{11,12} and Bossaerts¹³ reported non-linear least squares programs implementable on programmable calculator. Dedicated instruments (stopped flow or temperature jump) shall process data with proprietary software and cannot directly be used in routine kinetic investigations. The software for response surface methodology using MLR and PLS in kinetics is not easily available. Stanley *et al.*¹⁴ proposed Regularized Least Squares and method of expectation maximum for the analysis of parallel first order rate processes. Eigen vector analysis is used as a part of the algorithm. They estimated 3, 5, 7 and 9 rate constants, their successive ratio being around four.

Weber *et al.*¹⁵ employed a hybrid method involving steepest descent and Broyden Fletcher Goldfarb Shanno (BFGS) procedures to estimate upto six rate constants for hydrolysis of iodine. Ventura *et al.*¹⁶ and Blanco *et al.*¹⁷ recently employed ANN in kinetic method of analysis. Corcoran and Rutan¹⁸ using Arrhenius formula and rate equation simultaneously has taken care of errors in rate constants due to variation of even less than 0.1° difference in temperature. It is especially useful for reactions of high activation energy. Rutan and Brown¹⁹ studied hydrolysis of *p*-nitrophenyl phosphate by monitoring the spectra in the region 390–450 nm and applying 3D Kalman Filter. Quencer and Crouch²⁰ adopted extended KF for the kinetic determination of 2 and 3 component mixtures of lanthanides with stopped flow diode array spectrophotometer at multiple wavelengths.

Swain *et al.*²¹ reported a FORTRAN program for rate constants using over-relaxation technique. It does not require initial estimate of *k*. Hibbert²² applied genetic algorithm (GA) for the estimation of rate constants of hydrolysis of ATP to AMP and ADP monitoring both phosphate and pyrophosphate. Booksh *et al.*²³ and Smilde *et al.*²⁴ adopted extended trilinear decomposition (ExTD) in multicomponent analysis of 1,1,1-trichloroethane, trichloroethylene and chloroform by monitoring spectral data at multiple wavelengths.

This is the basis to develop KINTOB with domain independent modules tailor made to tackle many problems of parameter estimation in kinetics.

Description of KINTOB :

KINTOB is a menu driven package and is developed in MATLAB which works even in WINDOWS. It runs on IBM PCAT in DOS environment.

Fig. 2. The method base used for different tasks of kinetics handled by KINTOB.

Preliminary experiments in developing KINTOB revealed that there are two types of procedures : one depending on principles of kinetics, and the other is independent but is of general use in any chemical task. The domain independent modules are chosen from the methodbase (Fig. 2) developed during the last 5 years in this laboratory. The programs for linear least-squares (LINREG), least medium squares (LMS), Kalman filter (ORD-KAL), Marquardt (MARQ) and Gauss-Newton (GN) have features of expert systems unlike those available in commercial packages. The heuristics are based on accumulated experience in this laboratory and elsewhere. The domain specific modules are developed to estimate rate constants by monitoring a reaction with a spectrophotometer at one wavelength or by titrimetry. The monitoring species considered in this context are reactant, product or excess reagent. The built-in facilities of 3D and contour diagrams of MATLAB are adopted.

The primary data for the integral order reactions, consecutive type ($A \rightarrow B \rightarrow C$) are simulated over different number of half lives. In order to understand the profile of the object function in the estimation of rate constants, simulated data sets are produced with range of *k* and a_0 or k_1 and k_2 . The data are rounded off to third decimal place to be in conformity with instrument readability. A uniform random number is generated by MATLAB. After suitable transformation to get a good uniform random number, normal random noise (RN) of desired mean and standard deviation is calculated. Separate set of random numbers is produced for each data set rather than taking subsets from a long series. A data set is produced by the algebraic addition of simulated data to the random noise. In order to mimic a true (real) data set, the random noise is produced a different number (6, 40, 100 and 8000) of times and the data sets which differ only in RN are

analysed.

The 2D and 3D profiles are useful to detect saddle points, discontinuities, linear or quadratic trends. This is instrumental for the choice of proper optimization function(s) and the optimization technique(s). A unique feature of this package is that after estimation of the rate constant, it automatically simulates the primary data using the estimated parameters. Thus a direct check and analysis of the residuals in the primary data can be performed. If the user chooses the option 'unknown order', zero, first, second, and third orders are tested. A condensed output of SD in Y, a_0-x and in regression parameters along with pointwise residuals and plots is given. The entire analysis discussed (*vide supra*) is performed with the suggested order based on minimum in residuals. Thus, in this phase it behaves like a tiny expert system.

Results and Discussion

There are five major options in KINTOB, viz. demonstration, calculation, simulation, interpretation and investigation. The flow of the software is depicted in Fig. 3. The package works either in interactive mode wherein the system prompts the user to give the input and infile mode where the paired data can be given as an ASCII file. Apart from these options, template concept^{25,26} is useful to analyze large number of data files generally in a research project. In this option, in addition to the ASCII

Fig. 3 (contd.)

Fig.3 (contd.)

Fig. 3 (contd.)

Fig. 3. A snap shot of User options in KINTOB.

file (XX.INP) (discussed *vide supra*), a parameter file (XX.Par) specific for that run edited by the user from the standard templates is used. When the command RUN is given at MATLAB prompt, the system asks the user to give input file and displays the results.

Demonstration mode :

In demonstration mode simulated and literature data files are available. The data files are chosen from research literature each representing a typical case to demonstrate the features of the package. Thus the package can be used as an on-line self-learning tool.

Calculation mode :

In this mode estimation of rate constants of any medium slow reaction following zero, first, second or third order can be estimated from paired data set (time versus concentration or instrument response). Here, the user can choose any one or all the statistical procedures — LS, LMS, GN, Kalman Filter — available in the tool box.

Data Set 1 : A typical first order data reported by Hovance and Ward²⁷ is analyzed with KINTOB employing LLS, KF and GN methods. All the methods resulted in comparable rate constant and initial concentration (Table 6). As the signal-to-noise ratio is very high, lin-

TABLE 6—COMPARISON OF RATE PARAMETERS BY LINEAR AND NON-LINEAR METHODS

Input : ward_01.par & ward_01.inp Output : ward_01.res
 No Guess of order reaction $n \cdot A \rightarrow P$
 Absorbance of reactant is monitored by spectrophotometer
 Expert system inference
 Predicted order (=1) is same for sd in residuals iny and $(a_0 - x)$

Method	k	a_0	sd _y
LLS	0.0408	1.704	0.009664
KALMAN	0.0408	1.704	0.009664
LMS	0.0405	1.695	0.000224
GN	0.0404	1.696	0.001134
LIT	0.0404	1.695	

Table-6 (contd.)

Time	Response	Y	Residuals in Y		
			LLS	LMS	KF
0.6000	1.6540	0.5032	-0.0052	0.0004	-0.0052
2.6400	1.5240	0.4213	-0.0038	-0.0004	-0.0038
6.1800	1.3200	0.2776	-0.0031	-0.0003	-0.0031
13.9200	0.9660	-0.0346	0.0005	-0.0018	0.0005
19.3800	0.7740	-0.2562	0.0017	-0.0016	0.0017
26.9400	0.5700	-0.5621	0.0042	-0.0021	0.0042
37.6800	0.3680	-0.9997	0.0049	-0.0000	0.0049
84.1200	0.0560	-2.8824	0.1071	-0.0000	0.0171
107.3400	0.0210	-3.8632	-0.0163	0.0395	-0.0163

ear and non-linear methods yielded similar results and one should be cautious for other problems on hand. The half-life of the reaction is around 17 min and the reaction is typically followed from 2 to 98%. The classical residuals given in the table are for the log transformed response. Although the random errors in the response follow normal distribution, the residuals in the log transformed response have a different distribution.

Data Set 2 : In the case of a second order reaction with different reactions the software tests whether the system adheres to pseudo-first order or stoichiometric conditions and estimates the rate constants. Table 7 contains the data for the reaction between *p*-bromophenyl chloroformate and silver nitrate resulting in 2-nitro-4-bromophenol. It is a second order reaction with different reactants of unit stoichiometry but with different initial concentrations. The second order rate constant k_2 ,

TABLE 7—RESULTS OF A SECOND ORDER REACTION (DATA SET 2)

N1 : 1	N2 : 1	$a_0 : 0.115$	$b_0 : 0.115$
Ratio : 5	$a_0/b_0 : (1)$	$b_0/a_0 : (1)$	
Expert system inferences (KB k_2)			
Rule : 1 (KB k_2); Pseudo-first order			
$a_0_set = 0.1152$ $k_2 = 0.005821$ SD in Y = 0.02351 $t_{half} = 1492$			
Time	Y	$Y - Y_{cal}$	% reaction
1.0e + 003*			
0.6000	0.0122	0.0000	0.0286
1.2000	0.0157	0.0000	0.0445
2.1000	0.0209	-0.0000	0.0583
3.2000	0.0273	0.0000	0.0681
Method	k	a_0	sd _y
LLS	0.005821	0.1152	0.02351
KALMAN	0.005821	0.1152	0.02351
LMS	0.005824	0.1151	0.000772
LIT	0.005821	0.115	

calculated for the integrated rate law is compared with that obtained from pseudo-first order rate constant.

Data Set 3 : A simulated data set with $k_1 = 0.01$, $k_2 = 0.06$ and $a_0 = 1.0$ for a consecutive reaction ($A \rightarrow B \rightarrow C$) is analyzed by the linear model adopting LS, LMS or KF. The estimated rate constants are in close agreement with the true values. Fig. 4 gives concentration profiles of A, B and X.

Fig. 4. (a) Concentration profile of product : (i) $A \rightarrow B$, (ii) $B \rightarrow P$, (iii) total concentration. (b) Estimation of k_1 by monitoring concentration of A. (c) Estimation of k_2 monitoring concentration of B.

Simulation mode :

The third mode is to simulate the primary data for an integral order and consecutive reactions. This is crucial now-a-days in the validation of models, understanding functional relationships over a wide or narrow range of parameters, sensitivity analysis and validation of a new statistical method for the task on hand. As the noise structure in any real data set obtained is unknown even after a rigorous statistical analysis, generation of data sets mimicking real ones from simulated data is essential. Keeping the present trends in the context of chemometrics, several options are provided for the noise. Normal of non-

normal random noise as well as systematic error can be opted. In the case of normal noise, a heterosedastic noise of a given mean and standard deviation, proportional noise or a specified percentage of the maximum element of the simulated data can be added.

When the number of data points is less than 30, even the normal noise produced with an efficient random number generator does not appear to have normal trend (Fig. 5). In the non-normal mode a few popular distributions — log normal, poisson etc. — and a noise structure with user specified variance-covariance structure will be incorporated in the next version.

Fig. 5. Histograms for random noise of different number of points.

Interpretation mode :

The fourth option deals with the variation of rate constants with concentration of the reactant(s) and with ambient conditions. The former is to arrive at the order of the reaction and the latter is useful to understand the nature of the species and the activated complex. LS, LMS and KF are used for this purpose.

Data Set 4 : The LLS and LMS analysis of the variation of rate constants for different concentrations of sub-

strate (Table 8a) gave the same order as there are no marked outliers.

TABLE 8(a)—DETERMINATION OF ORDER OF A REACTION (DATA SET 4)

Regression parameter	LMS LLS	
	Intercept	-1.18
Slope	2.01	2.00

Concn.	log k (y)	$y - y_{cal}$	
		LMS	LLS
-9.5900e-001	-3.1146e+000	8.8818e-016	1.0623e-003
-8.2189e-001	-2.8416e+000	3.3194e-003	-6.5402e-004
-7.0952e-001	-2.6253e+000	1.3379e-002	-9.3999e-003
-6.3078e-001	-2.4486e+000	-4.6506e-003	9.5503e-003
-5.6051e-001	-2.3116e+000	8.8818e-016	5.7213e-003
-4.8452e-001	-2.1713e+000	1.2890e-002	-6.2799e-003
sd in log k		0.009718	0.007958

TABLE 8(b)—ELIMINATION OF OUTLIERS THROUGH LMS ANALYSIS

Point no.	$y - y_{cal}$						Data set 5	
	LMS	LLS	LMS	LLS	LMS	LLS	1/D	log(k)
1	1.74*	-0.91	Eliminated				0.528	-5.301
2	0.26	0.28	0.26	-0.10	0.00	-0.1	0.416	-3.596
3	0.00	0.62	0.00	0.19	0.28	0.0	0.448	-3.400
4	-0.04	0.41	-0.04	0.11	0.25	0.1	0.349	-3.154
5	0.05	-0.06	0.05	-0.16	0.03	-0.0	0.204	-2.954
6	0.07	-0.13	0.07	-0.21	0.00	-0.0	0.185	-2.935
7	-0.08	-0.18	-0.08	-0.15	0.09	0.0	0.101	-2.602
8	0.00	-0.41	0.00	-0.30	0.03	-0.0	0.046	-2.576
9	-0.61*	0.17	-0.61*	0.29	Eliminated		0.039	-1.950
10	-0.67*	0.21	-0.67	0.34	Eliminated		0.027	-1.860
	-2.48	-1.94	-2.48	-2.11	-2.40	-2.44	Intercept	
	-2.04	-4.64	-2.05	-3.29	-2.85	-2.35	Slope	
	0.70	0.47	0.36	0.25	0.17	0.11	SD in y	

*Outlier.

Data Set 5 : The variation of k with substituents or solvent parameters (Table 8b) resulted in different slope and intercept as an outlier (the *ortho*-compound) or solute-solvent interaction has pronounced influence on the regression line (Fig. 6). In such instances LMS gives correct regression parameters and detects the outliers in x , y or in both directions. As LMS parameters are biased, the package removes the outlier and applies LS to get unbiased estimators. This hybrid procedure is the best choice although not available in many packages. As KINTOB lists the residuals, either the residuals or the data can be fit in empirical (polynomial) model.

Investigation mode : The fifth choice has unique fea-

Fig. 6. Least-squares (—), least median squares (----) and experiment points (*): (a) full data set, (b) point number 1 eliminated and (c) point 1,9,10 eliminated.

tures with a provision to investigate the error surfaces with user chosen values of rate of constants, initial or final response, operating conditions etc. The optimum operating conditions for the estimation of concentrations in the kinetic method of analysis can be arrived at by MLR, 2D and 3D graphics and canonical analysis.

Data Set 6: A typical data set with $k = 1.0e-3$ and $a_0 = 1.0$ is used to study trends in the error sum of squares (ESS) in response as a function of a_0 and k . The software module $k_sim_k_a.m$ automatically generates the set of a_0 's and k 's based on the user opted number of steps. Fig. 7 displays 2D and 3D plots along with those mimicking univariate experiments.

Monte-Carlo experiments:

The SD's and joint confidence intervals for the estimated rate parameters by MLE (maximum likelihood estimator) are over-estimated. In order to arrive at realistic confidence intervals which are useful in the interdisciplinary research, Monte-Carlo methods have been proved as versatile. A perusal of the literature reveals that 100 to one million simulations have been attempted. At the end of each Monte-Carlo experiment, mean, median and SD of k and a_0 vectors (Table 9) are calculated. These statistics give the realistic confidence intervals unlike those obtained by LS. A point of caution is that the number of points in the simulated data set, their range and noise structure play a role in the end-result.

Contemplated modes in KINTOB:

The present package estimates rate constants for measurements at a single sensor. Extension for the analysis

Fig. 7. Variation of ESS with (a) initial concentration, a_0 , (b) rate constant, k , (c) response surface and (d) contour diagram for simultaneous variation of a_0 and k .

TABLE 9—STATISTICS OF RATE PARAMETERS BY MONTE-CARLO EXPERIMENTS

$k = 0.01, a_0 = 1.0, RN(\text{mean}) = 0, SD = 0.01$

No. of expt.	k			a_0		
	Mean	Median	Std	Mean	Median	Std
6	0.00999	0.01004	0.000516	1.004	1.007	0.0489
10	0.00999	0.00989	0.000385	0.999	0.991	0.0365
40	0.01012	0.01012	0.000378	1.012	1.005	0.0362
100	0.01001	0.00998	0.000314	1.000	0.997	0.0312
500	0.01004	0.01003	0.000352	1.003	1.002	0.0330
1000	0.01006	0.01005	0.000374	1.006	1.004	0.0362

RN = Normal random noise.

of data monitored at several wavelengths is in progress. In this context modifications in the data preparation modules alone are necessary.

The modules in MATLAB for advanced mathematical algorithms, KF (extended, adaptive), Simplex (super modified), simulated annealing algorithm (SAA), GA

and Fuzzy Logic are under rigorous testing in our laboratory with standard test data to arrive at convergence criteria in chemical tasks. These methods will fine-tune the rate constants or concentrations obtained by the gradient procedures and tackle chemical reactions with ratios of rate constants less than 5. These soft modelling procedures, direct search techniques and self-starting algorithms increase the capabilities of KINTOB.

Conclusions :

KINTOB estimates the rate constants of integral order reactions by LLS, LMS, Kalman filter and non-linear least-squares. The order with respect to a component and variation of rate constants with ambient conditions (T , μ , solvent) can be analyzed by LMS (if outliers are suspected) followed by LS. The standard templates make data preparation an easy task. Interactive and demonstration modes are user-friendly and are instrumental for Intelligent Computer Augmented Instruction (ICAI) like GUIDON. The unique feature of KINTOB is that it tests all four orders (zero to 3) in one of its options (order unknown). Apart from usual residuals and SD's, it outputs many other residual characteristics for peer scrutiny of models. Simulations of response after analysis of experimental data, Monte-Carlo simulations and 2D contours for a range of k 's are powerful tools to understand even complex kinetic reactions. Experimental design and response surface methodology will increase sensitivity in the kinetic method of analysis. A provision is made for different monitoring species in data input.

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